

INTEGRATION OF PHYSICAL AND VIRTUAL TESTS FOR ACHIEVING HIGH CONFIDENCE IN FATIGUE RELIABILITY OF AUTOMOTIVE BATTERY SYSTEMS

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In a concerted effort to minimise humanity's adverse impact on our environment, the automotive industry is keen to develop new and innovative solutions for a carbon-neutral future. They therefore face a critical requirement to offer extended warranties on new and relatively unfamiliar technologies such as advanced battery systems. This paper considers how the existing simulation, verification, and validation design process, may be enhanced to offer significant improvements in predicted confidence. Particular attention is paid to simulating the physical fatigue qualification test using a process called 'virtual testing'. This allows simulation to be better verified using evidence from fewer physical tests. The paper highlights the need for additional low-cost measurements during testing and a need to test to failure. It considers how virtual and physical tests may be integrated into a typical automotive design management process. It demonstrates how these tests mutually benefit one another.

Keywords: Electric Vehicle, Battery, Fatigue, Reliability

INTRODUCTION

All new electric vehicles (EV) sold in the US require a 10 year / 150,000 mile (240,000 km) battery warranty. EV batteries are complex mechanical structures that transmit structural and vibration loading through many thousands of joints and components. Fatigue failure therefore presents a significant risk to the overall reliability of the battery system.

Over a population of electric vehicles, the design target is often expressed in terms of a statistical reliability; for example:

“For a **duty cycle** of 10 years / 150,000 miles, I require a **reliability** exceeding 95% (i.e. fewer than 5% failures), at a **confidence level** of at least 90%.”

The statistical reliability target comprises three parts:

1. **Duty cycle** (or period) is a minimum duration over which the component is expected to function properly and reliably. This can be expressed in different units depending on the failure mode, for example: exposure duration, distance travelled, number of start-up/shut-down cycles, or charge/discharge cycles.

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2. **Reliability** is a minimum reliability target, or conversely, the maximum number of failures that are acceptable over the specified duty cycle. This will vary depending on the criticality of the failure mode in terms of both safety and economic risk.
3. **Confidence level** is a measure of confidence in the fatigue life estimation. It is based on the statistical distribution of life and the experimental sample size. The larger the sample, the higher the confidence. For small sample sizes, a high additional safety margin is required to achieve the desired confidence level.

Component durability is traditionally validated through a qualification (or sign-off) test. Historically, these binary tests (either pass or fail) were derived based on many years of production experience – in some cases more than 50 years. If a prototype passed the test without failure, it was deemed there was sufficient confidence to certify the component. However, in the case of EV batteries, much of this technology is brand new, and tests are often based on limited real-life experience.

This paper considers how digital simulation, combined with physical component testing and statistical reliability analysis, are used to support the fatigue reliability requirement and thereby reduce a company's exposure to unacceptable warranty risks.

FATIGUE MECHANISMS IN EV BATTERY SYSTEMS

A traditional 12V automotive battery is a compact, low-cost unit. In contrast, an EV battery system is an expensive, heavy (typically more than 500kg), physically large, high-voltage assembly of complex components. These complex mechanical structures support considerable internal masses. They also transmit structural road loads and vibration through many thousands of joints and components. As such, they often form an integral part of the structural body-in-white. A photograph of a typical EV battery pack is given in figure 1.

FIGURE 1 Photograph of a typical EV battery

EV battery packs often comprise of a number of subassemblies called 'modules'. These, in turn, comprise of many electro-chemical cells. Cells can take several configurations ranging from traditional cylindrical (C-cells), to prismatic cells configured as laminated foil pouches or in hard cases as illustrated in figure 2. Cells are connected electrically and structurally through a busbar. There are many different configurations available, however, they all require electrical and structural joints of some form (Brand et al. [1], Lee et al. [2], Amin and Gandhi [3]).

FIGURE 2 An example of different types of cell and their structural fixing in modules.

Design FMEA (Failure Modes and Effects Analysis) performed by the authors revealed fatigue to be a critical failure mode in EV battery systems. The root cause is attributable to a combination of structural, vibration, and thermal loading summarised below:

- **Structural loading** takes the form of low to high-cycle random and deterministic loads. These originate from two sources:
 1. the inertial effect of vehicle body motion on the heavy battery modules.
 2. multiaxial chassis loads which occur when the EV battery pack forms an integral part of the vehicle structure.

The requirement to reduce overall vehicle weight, whilst simultaneously providing crash, fire, electrical, and environmental protection to the internal battery systems, is also driving a requirement to use relatively novel materials and jointing techniques. As the battery system forms an integral part of the vehicle structure, this presents an interesting challenge when modelling the battery as part of the body-in-white.

- **Vibro-isothermal loading** occurs in the internal structure of battery packs and modules. It often takes the form of high-cycle random loads originating from road surface roughness, with possible high-frequency vibration from the electrical machine.

Temperature cycles occur at a much lower frequency than the vibration loads. In most cases it is sufficient to model fatigue as random vibration under isothermal conditions. The temperature effects are modelled by modifying the SN (Stress-Life) curve for the effects of temperature, and considering constrained thermal expansion as a static mean stress.

In some cell arrangements, damping was found to be significantly variable ranging from 0% of critical when cold, to over 10% when warm. The damping is also highly non-linear which adds further complications to the dynamic modelling of the structure and its ability to resist resonance-induced fatigue, especially at lower temperatures.

- **Thermomechanical loading** occurs in the internal structure of battery packs and modules. It often takes the form of low-cycle fatigue loading due to constrained thermal expansion during vehicle start-up/shut-down, charge/discharge, and high power transient cycles.

As well as failure in the battery chassis system and control module, another common failure mode is the progressive failure of the numerous joints between the cells and the structural busbar. Whilst each failure is in itself not catastrophic, it does lead to a progressive loss of charge capacity in the battery. Furthermore, failures can cause local stiffness changes which may lead to preferential failure sites in neighbouring joints. For more information on fatigue analysis, vibration fatigue, and thermomechanical fatigue, the reader is referred to (Halfpenny [4], Lee et al. [5], Halfpenny and Kihm [6], and Halfpenny et al. [7]) respectively.

BENEFITS OF COMBINING VIRTUAL AND PHYSICAL TESTS

In an efficient design process, simulation and physical testing are mutually complementary. This has not always been true of historical qualification tests because many of these predate the introduction of simulation. It has also been common practice for simulation engineers to model automotive components in situ as part of the body-in-white, but omit to model the component as mounted in the test fixture. In this case the simulation is unable to offer useful insight into the test, and the test cannot be used to verify and improve the accuracy of the simulation model. This section demonstrates that a properly verified simulation, used alongside physical tests, provides significant statistical confidence in the fatigue reliability of automotive battery systems.

It is reassuring to recognise that a traditional qualification test can be enhanced to incorporate the benefits of simulation in a relatively simple and cost-effective manner. Only three enhancements are usually necessary:

1. The need to simulate the component as mounted in the test fixture – virtual testing.
2. The need for additional physical test instrumentation to verify the stress simulation.
3. The need to run physical tests to failure to verify the fatigue simulation.

Comparing the fatigue life of simulation with physical tests is not trivial. The fatigue failure mechanism results in significant variability in the measured lives. For example, a sample of five apparently identical material coupons are likely to exhibit a factor of 2 difference in fatigue life. This is not because fatigue theory is mathematically uncertain, it is because fatigue initiates as a microstructural phenomenon, and no two coupons are the same at this scale. Furthermore, fatigue is exponentially proportional to stress, and, despite our attempts to linearize it, damage accumulates throughout its life in a non-linear, sequence-dependent fashion. Progressing from material coupons to real-world applications typically increases the variability from a factor of 2, to a factor of between 3 and 5, and it is not uncommon to observe factors of 10 in more complex components or applications.

If simulation is to be properly verified through physical testing, uncertainties in the input loads, material properties, and the analysis model must be properly estimated. The topic of uncertainty propagation and statistical reliability analysis is addressed in detail by Halfpenny et al. [8] and [9].

Benefits of simulation prior to physical testing

Firstly, simulation is used to determine the probability of passing the qualification test. It estimates the safety margins at an early stage of design. This allows for design optimisation to reduce cost and weight. It also offers confidence prior to expensive prototype procurement.

Case study: Virtual testing of a battery module showed a fatigue safety factor of less than 2 for a particular cell/end-tab weld. Simply moving the fixing point of the bus bar by a few millimetres sufficiently changed the stiffness and extended the life to a safety factor exceeding 3. Virtual testing therefore increased reliability and vehicle range at zero cost to the project.

Secondly, simulation is used to predict failure modes and locations. This offers early confirmation that the failure modes correlate with expectation based on previous experience, or that gained through FMEA. It is also useful in identifying whether a failure mode is obvious or subtle. Additional instrumentation may be required to detect subtle failures, whilst safety precautions may be required to protect people and equipment from the most catastrophic failure modes.

Case study: The failure mode identified in the previous cases study was difficult to identify visually; however it was clearly identified by a laser vibrometer, or by the test engineer ‘flicking’ the end tabs with their finger to see if they were loose.

Finally, simulation is used to model the extent of any beneficial or detrimental effects resulting from test simplifications.

Case study: A BMS (Battery Management System) was tested on a uniaxial shaker table where each axis was excited separately in a sequentially fashion. A virtual comparison was made with a 3-axis multiaxial shaker table where the same PSD loads were applied simultaneously. Virtual testing verified the same failure modes for both tests. The comparison showed the multiaxial test to be 2.32 times more damaging than the sequential test. Furthermore, the multiaxial test was less than 1/3 the duration of the sequential test, and did not require effort to remount the test article between tests. The multiaxial test was also easier to extend to failure than the sequential test (Halfpenny and Vervoort [10]).

Benefits of simulation during physical testing

Historically, many qualification test articles were sparsely instrumented. With the advent of simulation it became beneficial to enhance the value of the test by incorporating additional cost-effective instrumentation. Simulation can be used to determine the optimal positioning of measurement transducers such as accelerometers, strain gauges, displacement transducers, and thermocouples, in order to better characterise performance. A detailed explanation of this method is given by Wickham [11].

Additional instrumentation permits a detailed verification of the simulation to be made. The use of virtual transducers allows the simulated response to be compared directly with test data. Comparison may be made in the time or frequency domains, or the multiaxial fatigue damage domain. A brief example of the approach is given by HBK [12].

Better simulation parameters may be obtained using measurements from the physical test. For example, modal analysis of test data are used to calculate accurate damping parameters as discussed by Ewins [13].

Case study: Modal measurements were taken on an early battery module prototype. These revealed an absence of effective damping at low temperatures. Virtual testing showed this would result in premature failure of the cell/end-tab welds at low temperatures. Unfortunately, this failure was missed by the physical test because it was performed under cyclic charging/discharging, where the temperature was always warm. The module was subsequently redesigned prior to production to ensure good damping over the entire operational temperature range.

The use of additional instrumentation therefore significantly enhances the value of a qualification test which leads to an overall reduction in costs and an improvement in model verification.

Benefits of simulation after physical testing

A properly verified simulation model significantly enhances the value of the physical test. For example, if the test article were to fail prematurely, the simulation model may be used to help rectify the fault. In many cases, differences between the simulation and test article are attributable to the modelling of fixtures, boundary constraints, modal properties, and material fatigue properties. Rectifying these issues permits the engineer to simulate the observed failure mode and then refine the design to avoid subsequent failures.

A properly verified simulation model offers reassurance on reliability risk. For example, a qualification test may run to 48 hours with no signs of failure. However, how many tests are required to ensure 95% reliability with a confidence level of 90%? Simulation helps by offering a clear estimation of the safety margin. For example, is this a factor of 2, 10, 1000, or 100,000? With continual pressure to reduce test budgets, it is important to prioritise tests that are demonstrably relevant to safety and reliability, over those that are performed for historical purposes.

Case study: An OEM (Original Equipment Manufacturer) intended to perform its regular vibration test on a large EV battery. The test was originally derived for smaller components on ICE (Internal Combustion Engine) vehicles. They identified that the large battery would have a significant effect on the dynamic response of the body-in-white. This would result in a different vibration spectrum to the original test. The vibration test was therefore modified to account for the new vibration environment. They also found that the vibration test failed to exercise the structural chassis modes of the battery system. A separate road-simulator test was therefore introduced to validate the structural failure modes.

Another common question is: should the test be stopped at the target duration, or run to failure? If the test is run to failure, then how long will that take? For verification purposes, it is important that qualification tests are run to failure and this is becoming more common. For example, a qualification test is scheduled to run for 48 hours. After this time the test article is found to be unbroken and has officially 'passed the test'. However, it is now increasingly common for the test engineer to increase the loading amplitude and continue to run the test to failure in order to obtain a correlation with the fatigue simulation model. The simulation is useful in estimating a reasonable amplification factor in order to reach failure in an acceptable period without altering the failure mode.

Note: In the absence of an earlier simulation model, it is common for test engineers to increase the loading by approximately 10% every 1/4 test cycle until failure. This progressive load increase is easily modelled and is used to verify the simulation.

A properly verified simulation model also permits the investigation of many additional design scenarios and load combinations. For example, simulation can identify certain demographics or usage roles that are more sensitive to reliability issues. This knowledge can help to develop predictive maintenance schedules or encourage fleet balancing to avoid increased safety concerns and warranty costs.

Case study: An OEM started to receive early defect messages from certain vehicles in a fleet. Analysis showed this was expected for this particular demographic and was already accounted for in the reliability target. However, they implemented firmware updates to extend the life and reduce maintenance claims.

Long-term benefits

Over the long-term, experience with verified simulation models is reducing the need for some physical tests. This allows test engineers to concentrate on the critical and emerging failure modes instead of scheduling time for non-critical historical tests. Many OEMs are developing a concept of Simulation Readiness Level (SRL) that is analogous to the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) concept introduced by NASA in the 1960's and discussed by Kimmel et al. [14]. An SRL of 1 would indicate no confidence in the simulation at all, whereas an SRL of 9 might imply a sufficiently high confidence that physical testing is no longer required to qualify this failure mode.

INTEGRATING VIRTUAL AND PHYSICAL TESTING IN THE DESIGN PROCESS

Figure 3 presents a generalised overview of the design qualification process commonly used in the automotive industry. The overall objective is to ensure a product's reliability target is met using a combination of simulation and physical tests.

- **Simulation** is used to design and optimise the battery structure and components.
- **Physical tests** provide an independent **verification** of the simulation model, together with **validation** that the reliability target will be met.
- **Virtual tests** simulate the component as mounted in the test fixtures.

This process, known as “Simulation, Verification and Validation (SV&V)”, is a core aspect of the modern automotive design management process. Although OEMs have independently developed their own internal design processes, they tend to share basic concepts with established practices such as: stage-gate (or phase-gate) (Cooper [15]), waterfall (Royce [16]), V-model (Forsberg et al. [17]), Lean (Sato [18]), and more recently, Lean-Agile (Leagile) (Juventino et al. [19]).

FIGURE 3 Simulation Verification and Validation (SV&V)

According to IEEE [20], the terms Verification and Validation are independent procedures that are used together to qualify that a product meets its technical and legislative requirements, and fulfils its intended purpose. They are often defined as:

- **Validation** – “Are we designing the *right product*?”

In this case, will these battery subcomponents, when assembled, fulfil their intended function properly and reliably over the required duty cycle? This involves a thorough understanding of how components will be used in the real world. From the perspective of road-induced vibration loading a detailed review of this is given by Halfpenny and Pompetzki [21].

- **Verification** – “Are we designing the *product right*?”

In this case, are we confident in our design, and do our simulations adequately represent reality? This involves a thorough understanding of the product’s response to failure modes, and how subcomponents might interact when scaled to full engineering systems.

Most OEM design management processes contain some variation on the V-model as illustrated in figure 4. The left-hand side of the “V” represents the decomposition of product requirements. Starting from the high-level business and customer requirements, these cascade to the low-level engineering requirements — these are often referred to as the ‘technical requirements’, and cover every prospective failure mode of every subcomponent.

The right-hand side of the “V” represents the reintegration of the low-level subcomponents, through the whole vehicle, and to fleet-wide operation and maintenance.

The “V” model ensures that every prospective failure mode is covered by an appropriate qualification test prior to the detailed design phase. We therefore design a product to pass a test, and ensure that the

test is statistically representative of the expected usage. A detailed review of accelerated fatigue qualification testing is given by Halfpenny and Thumati [22].

The requirements of PLM (Product Lifecycle Management) are discussed by Grieves [23] and Tahera [24]. These extend the traditional “V” to consider the product from inception through design, manufacture, and disposal; where ‘disposal’ of EV battery components may encompass options for Reuse, Remanufacture and Recycle, as part of a larger Circular Economy as discussed by Bocken et al. [25].

FIGURE 4 The “V” Model (Paul et al. [26])

It is imprudent to leave all the qualification testing to the end of the design cycle. Reliability engineers often refer to the “Factor of 10 Rule” (ReliaSoft [27]), which suggests that the cost impact of late-stage design modifications increases with a factor of 10 with each stage-gate of the design process. It is therefore prudent to test and remedy potential faults as early as possible. Verification and Validation in the automotive industry therefore tends to take place throughout the design process and not just at the end.

Tahera [24] presents an example of a stage-gate process for a new engine product as illustrated in figure 5. In this case, fatigue design takes place through stages 2 to 5, with detailed simulation, verification and validation taking place through stages 2 to 4.

FIGURE 5 Stage-gate process for new product introduction [24]

A common requirement of stage-gating is to ensure completion of all aspects of the staged work prior to passing through the stage-gate. Such inflexibility of timing can have a severe impact on product quality as described by the proverbial “Iron Triangle” of project management illustrated in figure 6.

FIGURE 6 The “Iron Triangle” of product management

With reference to figure 6, “Functionality” represents a product’s requirements, “Cost” represents the available resources, and “Time” represents the time available prior to an inflexible stage-gate. “Quality” is therefore a function of Functionality, Cost, and the Time available.

The principal of the “Iron Triangle” is that there must be flexibility in at least one of the three vertices of the triangle. In the case of most automotive battery components, the requirement specification (Functionality) is relatively fixed, as is the resource allocation (Cost), therefore any attempt to unduly

constrain Time will have a detrimental impact on product quality. This is particularly problematic with the many novel design concepts introduced by EVs. A requirement to loosen the constraints on time has therefore been highlighted for EVs and is addressed here.

Fatigue reliability is an aging mechanism and therefore necessitates relatively long tests which are typically performed at the end of the stage. It is quite common for tests to overrun the stage-gate. Tahera [28] addresses this through a proposed overlapping methodology illustrated in figure 7.

FIGURE 7 Process flow diagram in the generic stages of concept development, design verification and product validation [28]

Figure 7 shows the design progressing through each stage-gate of the process using a combination of CAE (Computer-Aided Engineering) simulation and physical testing. The physical tests are allowed to traverse the stage-gate in a managed way — the stage-gate is effectively ‘kinked’ around the testing. The results of testing are continually fed back to the simulation team to help in the verification and incremental improvement of the simulation models as discussed in section 3.

Combining simulation with product design (A in figure 7), allows engineers to perform design optimisation early in the product development cycle. This improves the maturity of specifications sent to suppliers (B) for prototype procurement. Virtual testing – i.e. modelling the component as mounted in the test fixtures – helps to finalise the test specification and establish instrumentation requirements for the verification process (C) as discussed in section 3.1 (Benefits of simulation prior to physical testing).

Accurate simulations require accurate modelling parameters. Although initial design concepts may assume estimated parameters to start with, it becomes necessary to replace these with more accurate measurements as prototypes become available. This ensures that the simulations properly model reality. These tests are often referred to as ‘parametric tests’ – i.e. tests that measure parameters for use in simulation. Examples include: modal tests (Ewins [13]), and fatigue tests (Halfpenny [29] and Lee et al. [5]). These account for the overlapping cycle (C) which is described in section 3.2 (Benefits of simulation during physical testing).

As design and simulation progress, information is released to suppliers allowing procurement of additional component prototypes. This release process occurs progressively (D) with a view to ensuring that suppliers of test prototypes are working with design information which is up-to-date with no need

to wait until the respective design activity is finalised. Each procured prototype can involve a mix of old and new parts depending on project progress (E).

The prototypes progress through two layers of physical testing at each stage (shown in the bottom part of Figure 7):

- **Performance tests** assess how well the emerging product satisfies its functionality requirements. These focus on characteristics such as charge/discharge rates, electro-chemical efficiency, modal response, and the temperatures of thermal cycles. Material fatigue tests are also referred to as ‘Performance tests’ in this context.
- **Mechanical tests** (or qualification/sign-off tests) are mainly undertaken to assure the reliability and durability of the emerging product.

Figure 7 shows that performance testing starts slightly before mechanical testing and runs almost in parallel. Any design issues identified through these physical tests are dealt with in the next stage of the process (F) which is described in section 3.3 (Benefits of simulation after physical testing).

This process shows how overlapping physical and virtual tests can verify and improve the accuracy of simulation leading to a rapidly maturing simulation model. The physical and virtual tests become mutually complementary in qualifying the product with increased confidence and fewer physical prototypes.

CONCLUSION

This paper considers how existing simulation models can be implemented as virtual tests by modelling components as mounted in the test fixtures. It demonstrates how these may be combined with their physical counterparts to offer higher confidence that reliability targets will be met for novel and high-value components such as EV battery systems. The key conclusions are:

1. Recognising that physical qualification tests take a long time. This is due to the lead time for procurement and/or manufacture of test articles, and the nature of fatigue as an ageing-related failure mode.
2. Recognising the need to simulate the physical test. This ‘Virtual Test’ simulates the component as it is mounted in the test fixture. It is necessary to verify the accuracy of the simulation model and to obtain improved modelling parameters. A verified model can be applied to the body-in-white model with greater confidence.
3. Recognising the need for additional instrumentation during the physical qualification test. This ensures that maximum value is obtained from the physical test. The physical test is used to simultaneously validate the design, verify the simulation model, and obtain improved modelling parameters.
4. Recognising the importance of running qualification tests to failure. This is due to the need to verify accuracy of the fatigue simulation. Section 3.3 describes how this may be performed in an efficient manner by avoiding the risk of excessive test durations.
5. Recognising the value of combining virtual test results with physical tests. This enables virtual test results to be combined with physical results to offer greater confidence that reliability targets will be met whilst reducing the number of physical prototypes required.

6. Recognising the long-term value of properly verified simulation models in reducing the number of qualification tests required. The evolving confidence in simulation models can be monitored through the concept of Simulation Readiness Levels (SRL). This allows test engineers to concentrate on the critical and emerging failure modes instead of scheduling time for non-critical historical tests.
7. Recognising the importance of overlapping virtual and physical tests in the design management process. This enables the benefits of virtual and physical testing to be realised as part of the OEMs product development process. It permits managed flexibility of the stage-gates to accommodate relatively long tests without incurring any risk to product quality due to overly constrained deadlines.

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